

Maize Business to Address Base of Pyramid (BoP): A Case Study on Bangladesh

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Abstract

The case study investigates the ways to offer innovative approaches in maize production and align maize marketing to address the extremely poor people, i.e., the “base of the pyramid” (BoP). Authentic BoP marketing strategy is directed to the extremely poor population, consumer orientation (with features of adaptability and consumer education), and fair and inclusive growth. The project facilitator seeks to have development outcomes of improved maize varieties (high-yielding, stress-tolerant, nutrient-enhanced), enhanced food security, improved livelihoods, better nutrition and improved health and reduced rural poverty. The case study approaches routes to eliminate the fundamental reasons of the poverty by following developmental processes to transform the whole situation. The project aims to facilitate communication and dissemination of results to all stakeholders in order to enhance knowledge of maize production systems. It also covets to provide synthesized and informative analysis throughout the inter-professional organizations' value chain focusing the rural farmers.

Keywords: Balance of Pyramid, Fair and Inclusive growth, Development Programming

1. Introduction

Maize, as the third most significance cereal crop of Bangladesh has been positioned right after rice and wheat. It became a major source of employment for Char dwellers, especially smallholders and women. Maize is cultivated in almost all the districts of Bangladesh except in Narail District (DAE, 2010). Import fills the demand gap and price prevails at import parity where world corn price dominates in the domestic market as well. Bangladesh usually imports from regional and neighboring countries, like India and Myanmar that have surplus in maize production. At present, maize is grown on only about 16.2 thousand hectares in the country (Quasem; 1999). Out of the existing coverage, Rajshahi division has the largest share (60%); followed by Dhaka Division (20%); though not all districts of the two divisions experience fast growth, except for Dinajpur, Dhaka, Bogra, Rangpur, Mymensingh and Kushtia.

As agriculture is the key determinant of the income level of around 70% of the country population; this would be scrutinized and sketched to improve the present condition of people, especially the small farmers. Bangladesh is blessed with geographical features that complement effective crop harvesting. Wetlands, hills, plains, riverbanks- the country boasts having all sort of geographical characteristics mashed up in one place. This diversity needs to be taken into account. (Bhuiya & Mohiuddin, 2013) Maize farming has improved the lives of thousands of farmers in the greater northern region. Owing to this, a full-fledged supply chain of maize production has flourished, creating more employment opportunities. (Dev & Nuruzzaman, 2006).

2. Purpose/ Objective:

In an effort to confront the challenges Bangladeshi maize farmers continue to face, the facilitators are partnering with Northern Producers to improve the livelihoods of maize farmers in various districts including Dinajpur, Dhaka, Bogra, Rangpur, Mymensingh and Kushtia. The target group in the maize sector is the small, marginal, and medium farms with a special emphasis in the chars and areas where summer maize is cultivated. In order to implement the project, all actors would work together to integrate farmers for getting access to remunerative opportunities in existing or new markets. The implementation tactic should be to increase production, improve resource productivity and secure access to post-harvest marketing opportunities. This would create new markets for maize businesses and help the target group achieve better access to finance. The facilitators aim to develop sustainable market mechanisms by intervening in five broad areas, such as:

- 1) Promoting profitable cropping pattern,
- 2) Improving access to quality inputs,
- 3) Expanding contract farming system,
- 4) Introducing technological innovation, and

5) Open access to new markets outside of poultry feed.

In a nutshell, the overall objective is to improve decision making in order to offer innovative approaches in maize production and align maize marketing focusing the rural people who officially live below the poverty line in Bangladesh.

3. Literature Review

3.1 Business at base of the pyramid (BoP)

Out of six and a half billion inhabitants around the globe, somewhat between three and four billion people are intensely stalled in poverty or at “bottom of the pyramid”. Also referred to as the "Base of the Pyramid" (or BoP), the term should not mean to disrespect the poor people; rather should be a concern for people living in affluent or other circumstances as this BoP is the prime source of social disturbances such as wars and terrorism.

The size of the population in developing countries such as in Bangladesh and Democratic Republic of Congo are 163 million and more than 75 million respectively. The noteworthy percentage of this population living below the poverty line (about 30 to 70 percent) along with the GDP growth rates (between 5 to 10 percent per year) of these developing countries has made BoP markets attractive. (see Exhibit 1).

Exhibit 1. Size and Growth of BoP markets			
	Population (in billions, 2013)	Population below the poverty line (%)	2012 GDP growth rate (%)
BoP markets			
Bangladesh	163	31.5 (2010)	6.1
Bolivia	10.5	49.6 (2010)	5.2
Burkina Faso	18	46.7 (2009)	8.0
Congo (D.R.C.)	75.5	71 (2006)	7.1
Ivory Coast	22.4	42 (2006)	9.8
Mexico	116	51.3 (2010)	3.9
Developed markets			
Canada	34.5	9.4 (2008)	1.8
France	66	7.8 (2010)	0
Germany	81	15.5 (2010)	0.8
United States	316	15.1 (2010)	2.2

Source: CIA, 2013.

Exhibit1. Size and Growth of BoP markets

Prahalad and Hammond (2002) opposed the above-mentioned idea as the poor have no money; and are too worried for fulfilling their essential needs to misuse their money on non-essential goods; and the BoP is not able to apply advanced technology. However, Karnani (2008) and Karamchandani et al. (2011) stated that it would be very impractical not to have any expectation from the consumers at the BoP. It is unlikely that due to lack of information, lack of education, and economic, cultural and social deprivation, the BoP consumers would turn to be irrational consumers, and delivering more consumption options with no increased impact on their welfare.

3.2 Business and the BoP

There have been many efforts to “make poverty history”, but the problem remains. It is seen that, most of the direct aids are coming from international effort, individual governments, non-governmental organisations (NGOs), charitable donations (individuals and bodies) such as churches, or from charitable

foundations where most of the aids are provided to deal with emergencies, such as famine or war. However, it is observed that, there is a necessity of taking attempts to overcome the fundamental reasons of the poverty by following some developmental processes to transform the whole situation with highest emphasis given on changing the entire situation. Though the non-governmental organisations and foundations work to fight against root-causes and create awareness of the needs and possible solutions in an attempt to remove poverty from the world, the business community with their strongest influence can help them make changes in the situation. Moreover, more emphasize is placed on the large multinational corporations (MNCs) as they can influence how the societies operates and because of the larger supply chains and smaller size, Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), are also getting attention to get closer to the action.

Actual BoP strategies involve active participation of local people in design, production, and distribution for developing a new product or services. The purpose of these products is to radically reduce prices compared to similar items of developed countries. Though these contexts are bracketed together by some unavoidable factors, including low purchasing power, lack of infrastructures, lack of organization and corruption, yet this creates opportunity to instill innovations in product design, production, employee training, distribution methods and delivery. This novel method leads to augment business-profit and also motivates the corporate social responsibility (CSR) practice by the related stakeholders.

3.3 BoP Marketing Strategies: Defining the Concept

Even though all BoP products and services target BoP consumers, there are various ways of defining and measuring poverty which focuses on study of different target populations (Kolk, Rivera- Santos, & Ruf'in, in press). Banerjee and Duflo (2007) stated that a poverty threshold would be of \$1 to \$2 each person, for every day where the number of this population worldwide was forecasted to be about 2.6 billion individuals (World Bank, 2011). Having this minimum income stream, consumers are hardly able to buy what they need. Hence, price has become a vital factor of BoP marketing strategies. As low price yields low profits, high volumes should be sold to ensure profitability; for which products should be easily accessible at neighbourhood stores at convincing low cost. Thereby, the hurdles to reach and deliver goods to consumers followed by lack of transportation and distribution infrastructures should be resolved. In a nutshell, to serve the BoP effectively, affordability and accessibility are essential features of product strategy. Prahalad (2004) stated that the importance of needs, education, and skills of BoP consumers and usage situation and constrains are also important for successfully designing BoP product strategy. London and Hart (2010, p. 154) stated that there is a challenge, to make products which is flexible to usage situation and, in terms of their living condition (such as an absence of refrigeration), skills and level of education (for example, reading ability) and culture (habits, values), products need to be modified BoP. Moreover, there is also necessity of education to read the instructions of using the products, therefore modification to consumers' needs and education become two features of consumer's orientation of BoP.

Finally, BoP marketing strategy is also concerned with development of local people and quality-of-life and wellbeing issues besides market orientation. Payaud and Martinet (2010) describe BoP strategies similar to advanced CSR strategies, in which business corporations target very poor segments (earning per day is two dollars or below) and produce new products and services to satisfy fundamental needs while maintaining a balance in the eco-systems. For this focus, BoP strategies similes humanitarian aid. BoP strategies also deals with the concept of fair and inclusive growth for long term development. Inclusive growth as a part of its public and business policy goals try to distribute resources towards programmes that works with poverty reduction and creating employment opportunities, also this growth strategy ensures fundamental services for the poor, equality of chances and empowering though skill building and education (George, McGahan, & Prabhu, 2012, p. 661). Given the targeted population of BoP, which are customers, employees, entrepreneurs, suppliers, subcontractors, retailers, or spokespersons; the inclusive growth leads to social innovation, Hence, authentic BoP marketing strategy (see Exhibit 2) comprises of:

- a marketing strategy directed to the very poor (with features of affordability and availability),
- consumer orientation (with features of adaptability and consumer education), and

- fair and inclusive growth.

Exhibit 2: The dimensions of a BoP Marketing Strategy

Eventually, it can be concluded that, BoP strategy deals with accessibility and affordability as very basic marketing strategy to ensure available products at low prices, then in terms of consumers needs, education and usage situation the products should be adapted, including educating consumers. Then it ends with ensuring equal employment opportunities, targeting them as customers, employees and other part of the whole system to improve their well-being as part of fair and inclusive growth.

3.4 Theory of Change:

A theory of change has two broad components. The first component involves conceptualizing and operationalizing three core frames of the theory. These frames define:

- Populations: who are being served.
- Strategies: what strategies would accomplish desired outcomes.
- Outcomes: what you intend to accomplish. The theory of change determines all building blocks required to achieve the long-term goal. This set of connected building blocks -- interchangeably referred to as outcomes, results, accomplishments, or preconditions is depicted on a map known as a “pathway of change” or “change framework. The framework is a graphic representation of the change process.

Contributions by the project facilitators include:

- Output(s): High-yielding and stress-tolerant maize lines and varieties.
- Immediate Outcome(s): Improved maize varieties (high-yielding, stress-tolerant, nutrient-enhanced) adapted and promoted by NGOs, and private seed companies.
- Intermediate Development Outcomes(s): Smallholder farmers adopt improved maize varieties (high-yielding, stress-tolerant, nutrient-enhanced) or increased yields of maize for smallholder farmers, amplified income of smallholder farmers and improved diet nutrition.
- Strategic Goal(s): Enhanced food security, better livelihoods, superior nutrition and improved health.
- System Level Outcomes: Reducing rural poverty.

4. Scope of Work (SoW):

Strategies for scope of work for the key facilitators are given below:

- a. Sustainable Intensification and Income Opportunities for the poor: The facilitator aims to both pilot and scale-up and scale-out profitable, resource-efficient maize-based farming systems with the aim to improve system productivity, resilience, and sustainability and increase incomes of smallholders.
- b. Integrated Post-harvest Management: The Integrated post-harvest management facilitator aims to reduce post-harvest losses and improve food safety and market opportunities through the commercial production and distribution of maize storage technologies (silos and bags).

5. The Business Case:

Just as other commercial starches, maize starch has many uses. It is used as food in puddings, soup and gravy thickeners, as cold or hot water laundry starch, as a preferential water absorber in baking powder, in the manufacture of confectionery, in sizing and finishing textiles and papers, as a binding agent in papers, in making adhesive pastes, in conversion to dextrin's, which are the bases of many adhesives, in syrup and sugars, as a binding and diluting agent in the preparation of pharmaceutical products such as pills and tablets, in cosmetics, etc (Project Ethio: Details of 400 Business Ideas). In addition the production of maize starch yields some by-products that have a high commercial value. Although it is primarily used as human food in developing regions of the world, maize is one of the most important raw materials for animal feed production and biofuels in developed countries. Maize is a favorite raw material for animal feed. It is cheaper than many of the other feed alternatives and provides the required nutritional content for livestock. As a result, over 60 percent of maize produced worldwide is used in feed production.

In rural northern region of Bangladesh, a maize farmer gains access to soil testing services, to market price trends that help him/ her decide what to grow and when to sell, and to higher prices for his/ her crop than he/ she may obtain in the local auction market. The new system is an innovation of a large maize-buying corporation, which also benefits from cost saving and more direct market access. Another important aspect for empowering the poor people is to provide proper financing facilities through financial institutions. Recently ideas have been coming out throughout the world that does not require handing over cash to the poor.

For instance, Katalyst is one such organization that is working with maize farmers of Bangladesh through sharecropping. (Katalyst, 2012) This process involves the land owner getting a share of the profit for his land and the farmer getting the rest for his labour (Sarwar, 2012). Since the poorest of people of our country are not very well educated, they lack the necessary skills and knowledge for maize production which may be addressed. Bangladesh is a developing country with a huge population living on or below the poverty line. Most of these people live in rural areas and they mostly offer physical labour as a mean of earning their livelihood. These poor and extremely poor people can be addressed as the base of the pyramid (BoP). The key aim of intervention is to enhance the maize farming and integrate marketing into maize production by addressing base of pyramid (BoP).

5.1 Schedule

Project Management Improvement Project – Phase 1	Effort Estimate in months	Planned Start Date	Planned End Date	Resource
Initiate Project and Centralize Core Activities				
Develop Project Charter				
Define Scope of work	6 days	--	--	Name1, Core Team
Define Requirements of resources (engagement of stakeholders)	7 days	--	--	Name1, Core Team
Identify High-Level Roles	2 days	--	--	Name1
Develop High-Level Budget	3 days	--	--	Name1
Identify High-Level Control Strategies	1 day	--	--	Name1
Consolidate and Publish Project Charter	2 days	--	--	Name1
Hold Review Meeting	1 day	--	--	Name1
Revise Project (if required)	1 day	--	--	Name1
Gain approvals	1 day	--	--	Name1
Plan Project				
Develop Work Plan				
Develop Work Breakdown Structure	12 days	--	--	Name1
Develop Project Staffing Plan	30 day	--	--	Name1
Develop Project Budget	7 days	--	--	Name1
Develop Project Control Plan		--	--	
Develop Communication Plan	5 days	--	--	Name1
Develop Quality Management Plan	10 days	--	--	Name1
Finalize Project Plan and Gain Approvals	2 days	--	--	Name1
Total Planning schedule before execution to the field	90 days (03 months) schedule			
Execute and Control Project (01 year 09 months schedule)				
Design Framework		--	--	
Intervention with technology and equipment Oriented firms	180 days composite schedule	--	--	Name1, core team
Communication with components of finance and insurance		--	--	Name1, core team
Intervention with labor and Transport Services		--	--	Name1, core team
Skills, Capacity and Empowerment Oriented		--	--	Name1, core team
Collaboration with quality seed seller		--	--	Name1, core team
Collaboration with Pesticide seller		--	--	Name3, Name2
Intervention with corn based food processing industry		--	--	Name3
Build the Framework			--	--
Write the framework content	--	--	--	Name2
Test the Framework		--	--	
Test usability with BoP	90 day (01 season)	--	--	core team, review team
Adjust project based on BoP and other stakeholder feedback	30 days	--	--	Name2, Name3
Implement Framework		--	--	
Move framework to maize production environment	330 days	--	--	Name1
Close the Project		--	--	
Conduct Post-Project Review		--	--	Name1, core team, review team

5.2 Resources:

Collaboration with quality seed seller: As a promoter,

the aim is to develop sustainable market mechanisms by intervening in promoting profitable cropping pattern which required collaboration with quality seed seller. Bangladesh Agricultural Development Corporation (BADC) has been the only public sector seed marketing organization which supplies 90-95% quality seeds (BARC, 1990) of the formal sector. Public sector endeavor for production and marketing of seed had begun in 1954 with creation of 22 seed farms covering an area of 2200 ha. The BADC had virtual monopoly and command over the quality seed market. The same situation is still now prevailing except vegetables and hybrid seeds which are supplied mainly by the private sector.

Among the private limited company, ACI Ltd., Ganges Seeds, Syngenta, MacDonald (Bangladesh), Supreme Seed Company, Blue Moon International Seed Producer, Inam Afroza, Metal Seed, Energy Pack-Agro Ltd., Getco Seeds, Getco Agro Vision Ltd., Northern Seed Ltd., Kishan Seed Int., Mallika Seeds Company, Supreme Seed Company, Aftab Bohumukhi Farm, BRAC, East West Seed Company, Tin Pata Quality Seed Ltd., Syngenta, National Seeds Co. Ltd., A. R. Malik Co. Pvt. Ltd., Sajeeb Seed etc are most prominent suppliers of quality seeds. There are several multinational agribusiness companies that are not directly operating in Bangladesh but have marketing agents for their products in Bangladesh. For example, marketing agents of Monsanto (American agrochemical and agricultural biotechnology corporation headquartered in Missouri) has been found to very active in the Bangladeshi farm land, pesticides and crop protection.

Using pesticide for maize production: 85% of pesticides are sold to farmers by local level retailers. These retailers are supplied by companies producing and/or trading such pesticides and medicines. The pesticide companies generally dispense their products directly to local pesticide retailers through sales representatives or dealers' outlets. The remaining 15% of the pesticides are sold directly to the farmers by agents and distributors themselves. Manufacturing and importing companies, such as ACI Group and Square Group are leading the pesticide business. Syngenta, Auto Crop Care, SAMCO, National Agricare, Reneta, Emacon, BASF, and Marshal are common name for collaboration.

Facilitator would work with both private and public bodies like large input companies and manufacturers (e.g. KBP, CP), local DAE offices, financial institutions (e.g. Bangladesh Bank, Agrani Bank) and local maize traders (as contractors). Facilitator also need work closely with new farmers having better access to inputs, finance and technical 'know-how'.

5.3 Integrated Collaborative endeavour:

Actors of related service markets			
Technology and Equipment Oriented	Components of Finance and Insurance	Labour and Transport Services	Skills, Capacity and Empowerment Oriented
Tiller Machine	Insurance	Labourers	Community Based Organizations (CBOs)
Irrigation	Micro finance institutions (MFIs)	Transportation	Government Extension
Sheller			Institutions for Human Capital Support
Drying (Chatals)			Capacity-building Supports
			Information Support

6. Findings

6.1 Risk management plan

Possible changes or uncertainty are key sources of potential risks to project implementation. Some of these are related directly to the maize farming business.

- **Production uncertainty:** Weather variations and biological pests might delay the project viability. Death losses from disease and adverse weather conditions are common in the North Bengal area.
- **Price fluctuations:** Due to adverse weather and other natural hazards price may fluctuate. From an aggregate level, low levels of maize production are generally associated with higher maize prices, resulting in a natural hedge; though this may not hold for the individual farmer.
- **Property losses:** Casualty losses can occur from theft, fire etc and are generally covered by insurance.
- **Financial risk:** The risk results from the use of finance by stakeholders as reflected by leverage. Leverage multiplies the potential financial return or loss that would be generated with different levels of operating performance of the project.
- **Institutional uncertainty:** Uncertainty associated with cost and availability of debt is reflected partly in interest rate fluctuations for loans and partly from differing loan limits, security requirements, and maturities, depending on the availability of loan funds over time.

6.2 Risk Mitigation Plan:

Risks	Assessment without mitigation	Measures	Assessment with mitigation
Pre-Implementation Phase			
Delays to the start-up of project implementation	Not significant	Donor agency of facilitator assures timely implementation of project	Not significant
Delay in consultant recruitment leading to delays in project implementation	Not significant	Facilitator outlines criteria and procedures with timeline for consultant recruitment process	Not significant
Fluid political situation and potential for conflict	Medium	Good governance, decentralized and participatory project implementation, strong involvement of community-based groups, and existing agribusiness structures	Medium
Governance: public financial management, procurement, and corruption	Medium	Anticorruption and strong governance requirements outlined in project implementation.	Low
Poor management or improper practices including lack of transparency procedures, selection, and decision making.	Medium	Adequate support for business planning, capacity building, due diligence assessment, and screening and implementation of agribusiness plans, contracted intervention groups are made responsible to monitor performance of maize production, information campaign of procedures, and annual consultations with stakeholders.	Low
Difficult terrain not allowing specialist staff to assess feasibility of and support implementation of each business plan adequately	Low	A filter: extremely remote applicants must demonstrate they have market access, so they should be able to travel to meet business plan service providers	Low
Project Implementation Phase			
Natural disasters such as landslides and earthquakes, and worsening natural resources situation resulting from climate change and exploitation	Medium	Environmental management plan and measures required for all agribusiness and partners provide advice, training, and finance for forest and rangeland regeneration, and climate-adapted technologies and processes	Medium
Slow implementation and poor market connectivity affecting product and input prices and agribusiness feasibility	Medium	Nongovernment outreach and business support with contract performance incentives Infrastructure supported by other projects Agro-Enterprise Centre contracted to link markets	Low

6.2 Evaluation Methods:

Consistent with the project's objective of improving decision making, the project would facilitate communication and dissemination of results to all stakeholders in order to enhance knowledge of maize production systems. It would also provide synthesized and informative analysis to rural farmers throughout the inter-professional organizations' value chain.

The facilitator would be the key responsible person for implementing the project. At the regional district level, one dedicated staff from each regional division would be dedicated for collecting data, compilation, communication and dissemination of project results to the central levels. The project would provide technical assistance and capacity building support to the population of BoP to carry out this function. Budget allocations under component would be available to undertake on-demand studies and field surveys relevant to the project implementation process. To collect production yield measurements and collect data, the facilitator would delegate responsibility to the research institutes and to agricultural market observatory at urban level respectively. Relevant public services and other implementing entities would also be actively involved in overall collection using measurement methodology. The project would finance two impact evaluations, at the mid-term and at completion, to assess outcomes and results on the ground.

6.3 Personnel:

6.4 Exit Strategy:

'Exit' refers to withdrawal from the operational area of externally provided resources, whether material goods, human resources or technical assistance. The timing and manner of completing its tasks depends on a range of factors. An 'exit' may take various forms: (i) moving into a second phase of a project; (ii) terminating assistance under a specific project; or (iii) ending its country presence.

An exit strategy for a project describes how the project would withdraw from a region or population while ensuring that the achievement of development of maize production goals is not jeopardized. Exit strategies are explicitly linked to sustainability. It also considers means of ensuring further progress towards these goals after the end of other stakeholder's technical and financial support. The goal of an exit strategy is to ensure the sustainability of project result impacts and activities, for which the facilitator of the project would complement its technical capacity in development programming along with appropriate project exit strategies. Facilitator would ensure that, its assistance contributes to the development of the community's

resilience, for which it would define ways to achieve gains during facilitator's presence and continue even after assistance ends.

In order to qualify as a strategy, the exit or graduation strategy of the project would fulfil the following criteria:

- Clear action steps to reach benchmarks and identification of those responsible for achieve objectives;
- Measures to periodically assess progress towards meeting the exit criteria and possible modification of the plan based on any unforeseen difficulty in reaching the benchmarks of maize production;
- A timeline (flexible to a degree) specifying when these benchmarks for maize production would be reached and when the assessments would be conducted.
- Exit strategies might be 'phase-out', 'phase-over' or 'phase-down'. The 'phase-over' is most consistent with previous strategies in that it seeks to transfer the full responsibility for project activities to other organizations, governmental entities, community groups or individuals. This type of exit strategy requires significant management and technical capacity-building efforts, which must be initiated at the onset of the project to ensure an effective transfer and the continuation of well-functioning activities. The 'phase-out' exit strategy involves the withdrawal of program resources by transferring responsibility to related group.

6.5 Sustainability

Sustainability of project interventions relies on the following elements: (i) if the key stakeholders from line ministries and professional organizations as well as representatives from primary beneficiaries (population of BoP) contributes to project design and content, thereby ensuring relevance; (ii) if the implementation is streamed into Government structures and rural organizations (including inter-professional organizations, rural finance entities, etc); (iii) if the "subsidiary principle" guides all field interventions by empowering competent decentralized entities to be responsible for implementing investmets and managing infrastructure; (iv) if strengthening rural organizations is integrally embedded in the project to ensure that physical infrastructure and other investments are well-managed and maintained after project closure; and (v) If practices are mainstreamed within interventions for maize productivity increase.

7. Conclusion:

Given the colossal size of rural population living at the bottom of the pyramid in Bangladesh, aligning a major cash crop like maize with BoP strategy has been rationalized throughout the case study. The study effectively provides synthesized and informative analysis to rural farmers throughout the value chain of inter-professional organizations. While the project considers complementing its technical capacity in development programming with appropriate project exit strategies; it also requires sustainability and proper implementation for ultimate development of community's resilience and growth. Further research can be done in the field or related fields focusing BoP to eliminate the fundamental reason of poverty.

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